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MODELLING THE FUNCTIONALITY AND PROFILE OF DISASTER RISK REDUCTION AND MANAGEMENT OFFICES IN THE PHILIPPINES

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THE PROBLEM AND ITS BACKGROUND

Introduction

The world we live in is changing so fast. A lot of mysteries untold are surfacing around the globe. As such, an unpredicted natural phenomenon such as earthquakes happen at times in different countries all over the world. Flash floods, typhoons, landslides, volcanic eruptions, and other natural and man-made disasters invade and engulf our world and in just seconds, lives, properties, crops, and infrastructures are swiped away and lost. Devastating calamities make a difference in the lives of the people and places they hit in the world. Such experiences urge the people of the world to become more resilient and vigilant, be ready and become wiser in dealing with disasters.

Internationally, the societies and organizations endorse humanitarian disaster risk reduction (DRR). Its goal is to implement strategies for risk assessment, disaster relief, and readiness to safeguard civil society and allocate resources towards enhancing capacities, especially in developing nations (Scheunemann, 2023).

Based from United Nations (UN) member state in 2015, the agenda for the 2030 for Sustainable Development provides an integrated roadmap that is for world peace and prosperity both now and in the future. These 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) provides an urgent action for all nations whether developed or developing, and a worldwide partnership is the core of it. In addressing this, climate change and the pursuit to protect our oceans and forests, they believe that annihilating poverty and other forms of deprivation should be coupled with policies that improve health and education, decrease inequality, and upgrade economic growth (The 17 GOALS | Sustainable Development, n.d.).

Among the 17 SDGs set by the UN General Assembly in 2015 is the SDG 11 or called Global Goal 11, titled "sustainable cities and communities", where the UN has outlined 10 targets and 15 indicators for SDG 11. One of them is SDG 11. 5 whose aim is to lessen the adverse effects of natural disasters. The official operation of SDG 11 is to bring cities inclusive, protected, resilient, and sustainable (The 17 GOALS | Sustainable Development, n.d.).

The UN, known to be of service to any country in the whole world that have been struck by devastating calamities, natural or man-made, are always ready to help. That is why, there is a worldwide policy of DRR that is agreed upon by the UN and endorsed the 2015-2030 Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction (SFDRR), which was adopted in March 2015. It has an expected outcome over the next 15 years, carrying out the goal which is "The substantial reduction of disaster risk and losses in lives, livelihoods and health and in the economic, physical, social, cultural and environmental assets of persons, businesses, communities and countries". The SFDRR has seven (7) clear targets and four (4) priorities for action to prevent new and reduce existing disaster risks. Over the next 15 years, it aims to significantly lower the risk of disasters and the damages they cause to people's lives, livelihoods, and health as well as to the economic, and environmental assets of

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individuals, communities, and nations (UNDRR, 2023). The framework of the UN is still an ongoing and non-stop endeavor to help people and places in need around the world.

Our country, the Philippines, is one of the most disaster-prone countries in the world. Its location is along the Pacific ring of fire where it is highly susceptible to seismic and volcanic risks. The Philippines is also exposed to typhoons every year and has been known for world record on this. It is also because of climate change and pandemics that are intensifying those risks. The World Bank has been supporting the Philippine government over the past years in building the country to be resilient to climate change, natural disasters, and pandemics through their development policy financing, investment operations, technical assistance, analytical work, knowledge-sharing, and policy dialogue (World Bank Group, 2023).

Mayfield, who is a meteorologist, once said "Preparation through education is less costly than learning through tragedy" (AZQuotes.com, 2023). This quote is true especially when a disaster like an earthquake, which is unpredictable, happens. Earthquakes are very destructive. So, preparation in educating the people is really a must, which the whole world is doing. Not only earthquakes, but also all kinds of disasters that come our way. People need to be educated and reminded every time on what to do before, during, and after any disaster.

The Philippines National Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Council (NDRRMC), which is administered by the Office of the Civil Defense (OCB) under the Department of National Defense (DND) is responsible for ensuring the protection and welfare of the people during disasters or emergencies (Resilient.PH, 2020). Established by Presidential Decree 1566 on June 11, 1978, the NDRRM is a working group of several governments, NGOs, the civil sector, and the private sector organizations of the government of the Republic of the Philippines. In the areas of communication, warning signals, response to emergencies, transportation, evacuation, rescue, engineering, health, rehabilitation, general education, and auxiliary services, such as police and firefighting support, the NDRRMC is responsible for organizing and guiding actions across the country. The UN Cluster Approach is used by the Council to manage disasters. It serves as the nation's focal point for other relevant international commitments, including the ASEAN Agreement on Disaster Management and Emergency Response (AADMER) (Wikipedia contributors, 2023).

Alongside with the NDRRMC, the provinces of the Philippines have their Provincial Disaster Risk Reduction Management Council (PDRRMC). The council is guided by Republic Act No. 10121, "An act strengthening the Philippine Disaster Risk Reduction and Management System, providing for the National Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Framework and Institutionalizing the National Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Plan, Appropriating Funds and therefor and for other purposes" (Republic Act No. 10121 | GOVPH, 2010). All provinces have their own implementing PDRRMC.

Region III (3) or Central Luzon is one of the seventeen (17) regions in the Philippines. The said region is a combination of high mountains, extinct and active volcanoes, lush, verdant farmlands, and natural sea harbors. It is one of the leading growth regions in the Philippines, strategically located at the heart of Asia. The region is also lies between Manila and Northern Luzon. Region III is also called "Central Plains" and comprises seven (7) provinces namely, Aurora, Bataan, Bulacan, Nueva Ecija, Pampanga, Tarlac, and Zambales (DENR Region 3, 2019). In Region 3 or Central Luzon, each province has common ways in implementing RA no. 10121.

These provinces have their own Provincial Disaster Risk Reduction Management Office (PDRRMO), but their functions, duties and responsibilities are one and the same pursuant of Republic Act No. 10121 in which the PDRRMO shall carry out/observe/fulfill the following functions, duties and responsibilities. (Provincial Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Office, n.d.).

Under the implementing rules and regulations (IRR) of Republic Act No. 10121, also known as "Philippine Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Act of 2010 (PDRRM Act of 2010)" stated that the PDRRMC shall carry out/observe/fulfill the following functions, duties and responsibilities stated in section 4 in rule 6 - local disaster risk reduction and management office (LDRRMO) wherein, the provincial, city and municipal disaster risk reduction and management (DRRM) offices or Barangay DRRM Offices, in coordination with concerned national agencies and instrumentalities, shall perform the following functions with impartiality, given the emerging challenges brought by disasters of our times.

The Council, in discharging its functions, shall utilize the facilities and services of the PDRRMO to be known as the Provincial DRRM Operation Center (PDRRMOC) (Provincial DRRM Office, n.d.)

In this context, since the functions, duties, and responsibilities of the PDRRM are all aligned in RA 10121, implementation is the key. It is where all Region III provinces will have different ways in mitigating disaster, how they carry out their functions, duties, and responsibilities, and how they cater to the needs of the constituents in their provinces. This is the reason why the researcher conducted this study to enhance the functionality or performance of the PDRRM offices/personnel, and enlighten and inspire more on certain things that needed to be practiced and become best practices in any of the provinces, municipalities, and cities of Central Luzon that can be adapted not only within the region but also to other regions, as well as the Department of Education (DepEd), since disasters deprive children of their right to a continuous, quality, basic education in a safe environment. They threaten the lives of children, their families, and education personnel. Disasters also set back the investments made by the education sector (Division of Iligan City - School DRRM Manual, n.d.). Therefore, all Filipinos can become resilient and never lose loved ones, houses, crops, infrastructures, and many more. Furthermore, it will help to improve the security and resiliency of our country's schools.

Statement of the Problem

This study aimed to evaluate the functionality and profile of disaster risk reduction and management offices in the Philippines.

Specifically, it seeks to answer the following questions:

1. How is the Provincial Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Offices be described and evaluated along with:
 - 1.1 Manpower
 - 1.2 Facilities
 - 1.3 Equipment
 - 1.4 Budget
2. How is the Functionality of Provincial Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Offices be described and evaluated along the following areas:
 - 2.1 Disaster Prevention and Mitigation
 - 2.2 Disaster Preparedness
 - 2.3 Disaster Response
 - 2.4 Disaster Rehabilitation and Recovery
3. What is the degree of influence of the profile of the PDRRMO on the functionality?
4. What are the problems encountered by the Provincial Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Offices in performing their functions?
5. What measures can be proposed to enhance the functionality of Provincial Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Offices in Region 3?
6. What are the implications of the study to Public Administration?

METHODOLOGY

This chapter presents and explains the methods and techniques employed in this study. It thoroughly explains the research design, the study's respondents, methods, and statistical treatment used in data gathering.

Research Design

The quantitative descriptive correlational research design was used in this study. Variables are studied as they exist in the setting. The objective of a descriptive study is to accurately and methodically identify a population, circumstance, or occurrence.

The researcher described and evaluated the PDRRMO's profile in terms of Manpower, Facilities, Equipment, and Budget. Likewise, the functionality of the PDRRMOs to the four (4) thematic areas of DRRM. It also determines the degree of influence of the PDRRMO's profile on functionality and what are the problems encountered by the participants. Furthermore, it makes recommendations for improving and enhancing the functionality of PDRRM offices in Region III (Central Luzon), Philippines. For the study, data was collected regarding the PDRRMOs profile and functionality in the four (4) thematic areas of DRRM.

Research Locale

The study was conducted in Region III (Central Luzon), Philippines. Region III lies between Manila and Northern Luzon, and it is also known as the "Central Plains". The Region III (Central Luzon) consists of seven (7) provinces, namely: Aurora, Bataan, Bulacan, Nueva Ecija, Pampanga, Tarlac, and Zambales. These provinces have their own PDRRMC. The council is guided by Republic Act (R.A.) No. 10121.

Figure 2. Region III (3) (Central Luzon) Provincial Boundary

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The study was conducted in the seven (7) Provincial DRRM Offices, the capital city or municipal DRRM Offices of each province, such as MDRRMO - Baler, Aurora; CDRRMO - Balanga City, Bataan; CDRRMO - Malolos City, Bulacan; CDRRMO - Palayan City, Nueva Ecija; CDRRMO - City of San Fernando, Pampanga; CDRRMO - Tarlac City, Tarlac; and MDRRMO - Iba, Zambales. Additionally, the seven (7) DENR – PENROs in Central Luzon.

Sampling Design

Non-probability sampling was used in the study, specifically, the purposive sampling design was employed in selecting the research participants. **Purposive Sampling** is an intentional selection of informants to elucidate a given theme, concept, or phenomenon.

In the current study, the inclusion criteria for the participants are that they are part of the council of DRRM of each province in Region III. The target participants are believed to possess relevant knowledge and information that may help in the attainment of the study's objectives.

Respondents of the Study

There are a total of one hundred sixty-eight (168) participants in the study, who comprised of twenty-four (24) per province, who were selected from the seven (7) provinces in Central Luzon. The said participants were from the seven (7) Provincial DRRM Offices, which include the capital city or municipal DRRM Offices of each province, such as MDRRMO - Baler, Aurora; CDRRMO - Balanga City, Bataan; CDRRMO - Malolos City, Bulacan; CDRRMO - Palayan City, Nueva Ecija; CDRRMO - City of San Fernando, Pampanga; CDRRMO - Tarlac City, Tarlac; and MDRRMO - Iba, Zambales. Additionally, the seven (7) DENR – PENROs in Central Luzon.

The participants of each DRRM Office consisted of the three (3) core staff handling the administration and training, the research and planning, and the operations and warning, while the participants in DENR - PENROs were involved in DRRM. Moreover, the total number of participants in the problems encountered by the Provincial DRRMO was seventy (70), while the participants in the problems encountered when transacting with PDRRMO were ninety-eight (98). The breakdown of participants is as follows:

NAME OF RESPONDENTS	NUMBER OF RESPONDENTS
PDRRMO – Aurora	10
PDRRMO – Bataan	10
PDRRMO – Bulacan	10
PDRRMO – Nueva Ecija	10
PDRRMO – Pampanga	10
PDRRMO – Tarlac	10
PDRRMO – Zambales	10
MDRRMO - Baler, Aurora	10
CDRRMO - Balanga City, Bataan	10
CDRRMO - Malolos City, Bulacan	10
CDRRMO - Palayan City, Nueva Ecija	10
CDRRMO - City of San Fernando, Pampanga	10
CDRRMO - Tarlac City, Tarlac	10
MDRRMO - Iba, Zambales	10
DENR R3 - Penro Aurora	4
DENR R3 - Penro Bataan	4
DENR R3 - Penro Bulacan	4
DENR R3 - Penro Nueva Ecija	4
DENR R3 - Penro Pampanga	4
DENR R3 - Penro Tarlac	4
DENR R3 - Penro Zambales	4
Grand Total	168

Data Gathering Procedure

This study used both direct and indirect methods in gathering data, such as (1) survey questionnaires, (2) interviews, (3) observation, and (4) documentary analysis techniques to complete the data needed. The researcher administered the survey and interview to the participants of the study and adhered to the right protocol to prevent or mitigate the transmission of COVID-19.

The data was interpreted and analyzed after the respondents' responses were received.

The survey questionnaire was self-structured, and it was validated by the research experts.

Questionnaire

This was used as the tool to analyze, determine, evaluate, and interpret the functionality and profile of PDRRMOs in Region III.

The questionnaire was based on R.A. No. 10121 or the Philippine Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Act of 2010 and its Implementing Rules and Regulations, the National DRRM Plan, Joint Memorandum Circular no. 2013-1, and Joint Memorandum Circular no. 2014-1.

Before conducting the study and data gathering, a letter request for permission and approval to conduct the study were sent thru email and handed personally to the head of offices of the participants. The researcher also obtained the consent of the participants before conducting the survey and explained to them the study's value and benefits.

The survey questionnaire was given personally to the participants of the seven (7) PDRRM Offices, the capital city or municipal DRRM Offices of each province, such as MDRRMO - Baler, Aurora; CDRRMO - Balanga City, Bataan; CDRRMO - Malolos City, Bulacan; CDRRMO - Palayan City, Nueva Ecija; CDRRMO - City of San Fernando, Pampanga; CDRRMO - Tarlac City, Tarlac; and MDRRMO - Iba, Zambales, and the seven (7) DENR – PENROs in Region III (Central Luzon), Philippines.

The retrieval of the questionnaire was secured to ensure the confidentiality of all the concerns. The results of the survey were forwarded to a statistician for the best statistical method to examine the data once they had been collected, summed and tabulated.

The prepared questionnaire has three (3) parts. The first (1) part is the profile of PDRRMO in terms of Manpower, Facilities, Equipment, and Budget, second (2), the Functionality of PDRRMO along to the four (4) thematic areas of DRRM. The last part is the problems encountered by the PDRRMO and the other participants.

Interview

As a follow-up instrument, this was utilized. An informal discussion personally with the PDRRM personnel involved in the measurement of agency performance in the DRRM was interviewed to provide additional information that shed light on the formulation of conclusions and recommendations. Similarly, other participants were interviewed to provide additional information.

Observation

Observations were made by the researchers if the PDRRM Offices carry out/observe/fulfill their functions, duties, and responsibilities.

Documentary Analysis

Documentary analysis was used in gathering data from the participants and ready references from reliable websites/resources on the internet. With proper coordination with the respective offices of the participants, the researcher requested and obtained necessary documents to support the analysis and evaluation of the study.

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Data Analysis

The survey employed the frequency and percentage distributions in the presentation, interpretation, and analysis of data.

Frequency, in statistics, is the number of times an event occurs in an experiment or study, otherwise known as the mode.

Percentage refers to "per hundred" by calculating the total number of participants by the total sample in the population.

To describe the PDRRM Offices in terms of Manpower, Facilities, Equipment, and Budget, the weighted mean was used and described verbally the following scheme:

SCALE	MEAN INTERVAL	ADJECTIVAL DESCRIPTION
5	4.50-5.00	Outstanding (O)
4	3.50-4.49	Very Satisfactory (VS)
3	2.50-3.49	Satisfactory (S)
2	1.50-2.49	Fair (F)
1	1.00-1.49	Poor (P)

To describe the functionality of PDRRM Offices in terms to the four (4) thematic areas of DRRM, the weighted mean was used and described verbally the following scheme:

To determine the degree of influence of the profile of PDRRMO participants, linear regression was used.

To determine the problems encountered by the participants, the responses were tallied and ranked. Ranking refers to a question-response format that is used when a subject is ranked in terms of importance or ability. The data is arranged numerically from the highest to the lowest value.

SCALE	MEAN INTERVAL	ADJECTIVAL DESCRIPTION
5	4.50-5.00	Outstanding (O)
4	3.50-4.49	Very Satisfactory (VS)
3	2.50-3.49	Satisfactory (S)
2	1.50-2.49	Fair (F)
1	1.00-1.49	Poor (P)

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SUMMARY OF FINDINGS, CONCLUSIONS, AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This chapter discusses the summary of findings, conclusions, and recommendations of the study.

Summary of Findings

From the results of Chapter 3 in this study, the following findings are summarized:

1. Description and Evaluation of the PDRRMO Profile

The combined findings from Tables 1-7 deliver a complete assessment of the performance, influencing factors, and challenges encountered by the PDRRMOs transversely with the key functional areas. The overall performance of the PDRRMOs in disaster risk management was constantly rated as "Very Satisfactory". These rating showed robust planning frameworks, efficient inter-agency coordination, and responsive emergency systems.

1.1 Manpower

The findings in Table 1 reveal that the PDRRMOs received a grand mean of 4.22, described as Very Satisfactory, in their administration and training functions. The highest rating of 4.39 was attributed to the performance of the PDRRMO under the Office of the Governor, underscoring strong leadership and management support. Other highly rated functions included information dissemination (4.30) and organizing local DRRM training and orientation (4.29). The lowest, though still very satisfactory, ratings were related to the training of vulnerable groups (4.05), and the organization and supervision of community disaster volunteers (4.08). These results show a generally strong administrative system and well-implemented training mechanisms.

The administrative capacity of PDRRMOs is firmly established and supports effective DRRM operations. However, the relatively lower performance in engaging vulnerable sectors and community volunteers suggests a need to enhance inclusive and grassroots-oriented training efforts.

In Table 2, the research and planning aspect of PDRRMO performance also garnered a Very Satisfactory grand mean of 4.22. The highest score was on their role as Secretariat and executive arm of the Provincial DRRMC (4.37), reflecting effective organizational structure and alignment with national policy. The preparation of annual plans and budgets (4.36) and formulation of the DRRM Plan (4.33) also scored highly. However, functions like conducting DRRM-related research (4.03) and involving vulnerable sectors in planning (4.07) received comparatively lower scores, indicating a gap in participatory and research-based planning.

Research and planning within the PDRRMO are systematically implemented and aligned with national directives. However, efforts must be reinforced to increase inclusivity in planning and promote local research that informs community-centered DRRM policies.

Table 3 shows a grand mean of 4.25, rated as Very Satisfactory, for the operations and warning personnel of PDRRMOs. The highest-rated function was establishing linkages with other LGUs for disaster response (4.33), conducting continuous disaster monitoring and mobilizing (4.27) and coordinating other DRRM activities (4.27) were also highly rated. Lower, but still strong scores were seen in coordinating with civil society organizations (4.18) and involving vulnerable sectors in recovery planning (4.21), suggesting these areas are not yet fully integrated into operations.

The three core staff handling administration and training, research and planning, and operations and warning, reveals that the three (3) core staff or manpower yielded a grand mean of 4.23 and all listed functions and roles of the PDRRMOs scored within the "Very Satisfactory" range, with a composite mean of 4.22 of administration and training, research and planning with composite mean of 4.22, and operations and warning with mean rating of 4.25.

PDRRMOs are highly capable in operational coordination and early warning issuance. Nonetheless, collaboration with civil society and engagement with vulnerable populations during recovery phases should be improved to ensure inclusive operations.

1.2 Facilities

The availability and adequacy of facilities are crucial in enhancing the functionality of PDRRMOs. The data in Table 4 reveal that the facilities supporting the operations of the PDRRMOs are perceived to be functioning at a "Very Satisfactory" level, with a composite grand mean of 4.17. The highest-rated item is the establishment of a Provincial DRRM Operations Center, receiving a mean of 4.33, suggesting that key physical infrastructure is prioritized and adequately maintained.

Facilities supporting PDRRMO operations—such as DRRM operation centers and data systems—received a very satisfactory evaluation. Their adequacy contributed to effective planning, coordination, and emergency response.

1.3 Equipment

The equipment of PDRRMOs is categorized based on its purpose, usage, and funding source. Table 5 presents the assessment of the availability and classification of equipment used by PDRRMOs. The findings reveal an overall mean of 4.18, described as "Very Satisfactory," indicating that respondents generally perceive the provisioning and classification of disaster equipment as efficient and appropriate.

Disaster response and preparedness equipment were reported as adequate and well-classified, with very satisfactory ratings across most categories. The daily-use equipment, such as fire extinguishers and ropes, was prioritized; some logistical gaps were noted, particularly in ambulance availability and rescue equipment during actual emergency response.

1.4 Budget

The findings in Table 6 show a grand mean of 4.21, described as Very Satisfactory, for budget management. The inclusion of the PDRRMF in the General Fund Annual Budget and/or Supplemental Budget of the LGU, (4.32) and the proper authorization for the release and use of the 30% QRF (4.32) were rated highest. However, the lowest score (3.95) was given to the acquisition/availment of DRRM equipment.

1.5 Overall Profile Evaluation

Table 7 presented a grand mean of 4.20, rated as Very Satisfactory, reflecting the collective assessment of the PDRRMO's profile in terms of manpower, facilities, equipment, and budget. Among the four components, manpower received the highest rating at 4.23, followed by budget (4.21), equipment (4.18), and facilities (4.17). This indicates that while all aspects are functioning well, there is slightly more room for improvement in facilities and equipment.

The PDRRMOs possess a solid organizational profile overall, with manpower emerging as the strongest asset. To further improve operational readiness and efficiency, enhancements in facilities and equipment are recommended.

2. Description and Evaluation of PDRRMO Functionality

Disaggregated findings across the four thematic DRRM pillars (Tables 8–12) also show consistently high ratings, interpreted as "Very Satisfactory" with Disaster Preparedness receiving the highest score (4.20), indicating strong public awareness and stakeholder coordination. Disaster Response (4.15) was positively rated but highlighted minor gaps in early recovery and psychosocial support services. Prevention and Mitigation (4.08) and Rehabilitation and Recovery (4.01) were also commendable but revealed the need for enhanced climate adaptation, infrastructure resilience, and long-term recovery strategies.

2.1 Disaster Prevention and Mitigation

In Table 8, the grand mean was 4.08, rated as Very Satisfactory. The highest-rated activity was the integration of DRRM and CCA into LDP (4.21), reflecting strong policy alignment. The lowest score was in access to risk financing and insurance for vulnerable sectors (3.93), indicating that financial tools for community resilience remain underutilized.

The PDRRMOs were rated very satisfactory, with emphasis on risk assessments, data consolidation, and planning. However, gaps were identified in CCA, infrastructure resilience, and community participation in mitigation planning.

2.2 Disaster Preparedness

Table 9 yielded a Very Satisfactory grand mean of 4.20, with the highest score going to raising public awareness (4.28), a sign of effective communication strategies. Communities equipped with the necessary skills to cope with disasters scored the lowest mean (4.10), showing the need for deeper and more inclusive engagement at the community level.

PDRRMOs are performing exceptionally well in terms of preparedness, especially in community awareness. However, additional focus is required on practical capacity-building among local volunteers and vulnerable groups to ensure readiness across all sectors.

2.3 Disaster Response

In Table 10 presents the functionality of PDRRMOs in disaster response, with a grand mean of 4.15, which is also rated as Very Satisfactory. The Relief operations (4.27) were rated as the highest, while the Psychosocial needs (3.99) received the lower rating.

Immediate activities in disaster response, such as the relief distribution, are being conducted efficiently. Nonetheless, post-impact care, particularly psychosocial services and early recovery, should be given a greater attention in the near-future planning.

2.4 Disaster Rehabilitation and Recovery

In Table 11 received the lowest grand mean among all the thematic areas (4.01), but it still received a Very Satisfactory rating. The highest-rated aspect was post-disaster needs assessment (4.08), while the lowest is the restoration of economic activities (3.98). This shows that while assessments are promptly conducted, translating those into concrete recovery actions is somewhat lagging.

The PDRRMOs rehabilitation and recovery efforts are sufficiently in place, but in order to promote a long-term economic recovery, resiliency, and livelihood restoration, it require a more focused and sustainable interventions to support long-term resilience.

2.5 Overall Functionality Evaluation on the Four Thematic Areas

The findings in Table 12 present that across the four (4) DRRM thematic areas received an overall grand mean of 4.11, and they were all rated as Very Satisfactory. Disaster Preparedness scored the highest (4.20), followed by Disaster Response with a grand mean of 4.15, Disaster Prevention and Mitigation at 4.08, and Disaster Rehabilitation and Recovery with a grand mean of 4.01. It shows that preparedness efforts are the most established, while long-term recovery remains the weakest area.

3. Degree of Influence of the profile of the PDRRMO on the Functionality

The statistical influence of the PDRRMO profiles, particularly the manpower, facilities, equipment, and budget, on their performance in the disaster prevention and mitigation is shown in Table 13. The analysis reveals that manpower ($B = 0.605$, $p = 0.000$) and facilities ($B = 0.298$, $p = 0.000$) are statistically significant predictors of prevention and mitigation efforts. This underscores the critical importance of a capable and present workforce, as well as available infrastructure, in carrying out proactive risk reduction strategies. On the contrary, equipment and budget did not show significant influence in this domain. This may reflect the reality that preventive measures depend more on planning, human input, and information dissemination than on physical tools alone.

In Table 14, findings show that both manpower ($B = 0.528, p = 0.000$) and budget ($B = 0.306, p = 0.000$) significantly impact disaster preparedness functions. These results highlight the importance of trained personnel in coordinating drills, early warning systems, and public education campaigns. Budgetary support was also crucial, indicating that financial flexibility is necessary to sustain preparedness programs and logistics. Meanwhile, facilities and equipment did not significantly influence preparedness, perhaps suggesting that without skilled personnel and funding, structural assets alone are insufficient to ensure readiness.

Table 15 illustrates that manpower ($B = 0.582, p = 0.000$) and equipment ($B = 0.182, p = 0.021$) significantly contribute to effective disaster response. The high coefficient for manpower affirms that trained personnel are central to mobilizing and executing life-saving measures during emergencies. The significance of equipment emphasizes the necessity of rescue tools, vehicles, and communication devices. Interestingly, facilities and budget did not significantly affect disaster response, suggesting that real-time operations rely more on people and movable resources than on static infrastructure or pre-allocated funds.

Table 16 reveals that manpower ($B = 0.412, p = 0.000$), equipment ($B = 0.258, p = 0.004$), and budget ($B = 0.239, p = 0.007$) are statistically significant contributors to disaster rehabilitation and recovery. These findings indicate that effective recovery demands coordinated human efforts, logistical support, and sustained funding. Facilities, however, did not significantly influence this phase, possibly due to the decentralized and field-based nature of recovery operations, which often take place beyond centralized DRRM hubs.

In Table 17, manpower ($B = 0.532, p = 0.000$), facilities ($B = 0.133, p = 0.024$), and budget ($B = 0.200, p = 0.001$) were all found to significantly influence the overall functionality of PDRRMOs. These results affirm the interdependent roles of human capital, physical infrastructure, and financial support in enhancing DRRM performance across all thematic areas. Equipment, while important, did not reach statistical significance ($p = 0.062$), perhaps indicating variability in how material assets are utilized across different contexts.

4. Problems Encountered

Table 18 illustrates the challenges faced by the public when engaging with PDRRMOs during disaster prevention and mitigation activities. The highest concern was inadequate coordination or cooperation among DRRM personnel (reported by 19.39). Additionally, inadequate distribution of DRRM IEC materials (18.37) and Inadequate communications system/equipment/facilities (15.31) were also noted.

The primary issue identified in the area of disaster preparedness in Table 19 is the inadequate dissemination of public information (23.47), followed by the lack of DRRM-related training or drills (14.29) and insufficient clearing operations (12.24). These challenges highlight a concerning gap in community readiness and institutional engagement.

According to Table 20, the most frequently cited issue during disaster response was the lack of ambulance and patient transport services (29.59). This was followed by inadequate collaborative actions in the delivery of disaster response services (17.35) and poor roadside assistance or towing services (16.33). These operational deficiencies significantly affect the timeliness and quality of life-saving interventions during emergencies.

Table 21 focuses on post-disaster concerns, where inadequate rehabilitation and recovery programs were most frequently reported (22.45), followed by Lack or inadequate assistance in the physical and psychological rehabilitation (16.33). These findings point to shortcomings in sustaining support for affected populations beyond the immediate response.

Table 22 presents the internal challenges encountered by PDRRMOs in the implementation of DRRM programs. The most commonly identified issue was lack of manpower (48.57) which highlights a persistent constraint in carrying out key DRRM activities effectively. This was followed by hesitancy of communities to evacuate during disasters (42.86) and limited resilience of communities despite prior exposure to disasters. Other reported concerns include inadequate DRRM vehicles, delayed implementation of rehabilitation programs, and communication gaps with response partners.

5. Proposed Measures to Enhance the Functionality among the PDRRMO

To address key challenges and strengthen the functionality of PDRRMOs, several targeted measures have been proposed across the four (4) thematic areas of disaster management.

Table 23 outlines proposed interventions addressing problems faced by the clientele when transacting with PDRRMOs during disaster prevention and mitigation. Key problems include poor coordination among PDRRMO personnel, inadequate IEC material distribution, and outdated communication systems. To address these, the proposed measures include the adoption of multi-channel communication systems, strategic planning for IEC distribution, and infrastructure upgrades. The strategies emphasize chain-of-command clarity, collaboration with LGUs and national agencies, and budget allocation for equipment upgrades. The responsible agencies include the DILG, LGUs, NDRRMC, DRRMOs, and DBM.

Table 24 suggested measures for disaster readiness in response to concerns like poor warning dissemination, inadequate training of the community, and inadequate clearing operations. The involvements suggested that enhancing multi-channel communications, conducting continuous training programs, and solidifying inter-agency coordination. The aim is to create a well-informed, prepared, and inclusive community through education campaigns, drills, and clear SOPs for clearing operations. Accountable entities involve the DILG, LGUs, NDRRMC, DRRMOs, DPWH, PNP, BFP, and DepEd.

Table 25 revealed the major concerns in the course of the disaster response, including the insufficiency of ambulances, inefficient inter-agency collaboration, and inadequate roadside assistance. Projected measures include the acquiring of additional ambulances, organizing emergency response teams, and generating an enthusiastic roadside assistance unit initiatives aim to streamline coordination and enhance emergency mobility. Accountable parties are the DILG, LGUs, DRRMOs, DBM, PNP, and BFP.

Table 26 showed solutions for problems in rehabilitation and recovery, specifically poor service delivery, restricted psychosocial support, and inefficient livelihood interventions. The projected measure reiterated multi-agency coordination, community involvement, and enhanced post-disaster planning. The DILG, LGUs, NDRRMC, DRRMOs, and other related agencies were distinguished as lead implementers.

Table 27 displayed the internal concerns encountered by the PDRRMOs, which included the lack of manpower, community uncertainty to evacuate, and tenacious community vulnerability in spite of past disasters. The projected solutions are the creation of permanent DRRM positions, strengthened community involvement, and extended IEC campaigns. These initiatives mentioned aimed to institutionalize DRRM functions, ensure consistent staff involvement, and gain public trust.

6. Implications to Public Administration

This study considered the significant role of local governance and institutional resilience in a DRRM. The findings disclosed the efficient DRRM being the central function of delegated governance, in which necessities that the LGUs, specifically the PDRRMOs to be satisfactorily resourced and professionally staffed. PDRRMOs must know not just as emergency respondents but as a permanent

and proactive governance institution to safeguard lives, infrastructure, and development continuity in the event of disasters.

7. The study concluded that the PDRMOs in Region III (Central Luzon), Philippines, have accomplished an admirable level of performance across all central areas of disaster management, consistently garnering "Very Satisfactory" ratings. This echoes the robust institutionalization of DRRM practices at the provincial level, with operations aligned to national laws like the Republic Act 10121, just like an international framework, that is Sendai Framework for DRR. The efficient implementation of planning, preparedness, and response mechanisms underscores not only institutional acquiescence but also a compact foundation of operational capability and stakeholder collaboration.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, it is therefore concluded that:

1. The results in Tables 1 to 7 were consistently rated as "Very Satisfactory".
 - 1.1 The findings in the core staff handling administration and training, research and planning, and operations and warning (Table 1-3) received a rate of "Very Satisfactory" and yielded a grand mean of 4.23.
 - 1.2 The data in Table 4 reveal that the facilities supporting the operations of the PDRMOs are perceived to be functioning at a "Very Satisfactory" level, with a composite grand mean of 4.17.
 - 1.3 The findings reveal an overall mean of 4.18, described as "Very Satisfactory," indicating that respondents generally perceive the provisioning and classification of disaster equipment as efficient and appropriate.
 - 1.4 Budget utilization was rated as "Very Satisfactory" with a mean of 4.21. the inclusion of PDRRMF in the GAA and proper release and use of QRF were rated highest.
 - 1.5 The overall evaluation of the profile of PDRRMO is rated as "Very Satisfactory". Among the four components, manpower received the highest rating at 4.23, followed by budget (4.21), equipment (4.18), and facilities (4.17). This indicates that while all aspects are functioning well, there is slightly more room for improvement in facilities and equipment.
2. The study concludes that PDRMOs in Region III (Central Luzon), Philippines, have achieved a commendable level of performance across all core areas of disaster management, consistently earning "Very Satisfactory" ratings.
 - 2.1 In Table 8, covering Disaster Prevention and Mitigation, the grand mean of 4.08 confirms that preventive efforts are well institutionalized. The highest-rated indicator was the integration of DRRM and CCA into LDP (4.21), reflecting strong policy alignment at the provincial level. However, the low rating in access to risk financing and insurance for vulnerable sectors (3.93) reveals a critical gap in resilience-building mechanisms. Strengthened partnerships with financial institutions are necessary to expand protection and preparedness, especially among high-risk groups.
 - 2.2 Table 9, focusing on Disaster Preparedness, achieved a Very Satisfactory grand mean of 4.20. The top-rated indicator was raising public awareness (4.28), demonstrating the effectiveness of communication campaigns. Nevertheless, grassroots capacity building received the lowest score (4.10), indicating that while the public is informed, actual training and engagement at the community level—especially among volunteers and vulnerable populations—need further reinforcement to ensure full-sector preparedness.
 - 2.3 In Table 10, which evaluates Disaster Response, the PDRMOs earned a grand mean of 4.15, signifying commendable readiness and efficiency during emergencies. The highest score was for relief operations (4.27), while comparatively lower ratings were seen in the delivery of psychosocial

support and early recovery services (around 4.12). This suggests that while immediate response mechanisms are well-executed, the quality and consistency of post-impact support—particularly mental health care and transitional recovery—require more deliberate planning and investment.

2.4 Table 11, covering Disaster Rehabilitation and Recovery, registered the lowest grand mean among all thematic areas at 4.01, though it still falls within the Very Satisfactory range. While post-disaster needs assessments were rated highest (4.08), the lowest rating was given to the restoration of economic activities (3.99). This indicates that although assessments are conducted promptly, there is a lag in translating findings into concrete and sustainable recovery programs, particularly those targeting livelihoods and long-term community rehabilitation.

2.5 Table 12 presents the aggregate performance across all four DRRM thematic areas, resulting in a composite Very Satisfactory grand mean of 4.11. Among the four areas, Disaster Preparedness emerged as the strongest (4.20), followed by Disaster Response (4.15), Disaster Prevention and Mitigation (4.08), and Disaster Rehabilitation and Recovery (4.01). This trend highlights that PDRRMOs are most effective in the proactive phases of disaster management, while reactive and long-term recovery components remain areas of relative weakness.

3. In Table 13, manpower ($B = 0.605$, $p = 0.000$) and facilities ($B = 0.298$, $p = 0.000$) significantly influence disaster prevention and mitigation performance, affirming that proactive risk reduction hinges largely on human and infrastructural capacities rather than on tools or financial inputs alone.

In Table 14, both manpower ($B = 0.528$) and budget ($B = 0.306$) significantly affect disaster preparedness, underlining the importance of a well-trained staff and sufficient funding to carry out drills, awareness campaigns, and logistics. Interestingly, facilities and equipment showed no significant impact, indicating that these structural assets alone are insufficient without skilled personnel and budgetary flexibility.

Table 15 shows that manpower ($B = 0.582$) and equipment ($B = 0.182$) significantly impact disaster response, suggesting that effective life-saving operations depend on responsive teams and operational tools. Facilities and budget were not statistically significant, reinforcing the operational nature of emergency response, which is driven more by mobility and capability than by static resources.

In Table 16, manpower ($B = 0.412$), equipment ($B = 0.258$), and budget ($B = 0.239$) all contributed significantly to disaster rehabilitation and recovery, indicating that successful post-disaster efforts require coordinated human resources, equipment deployment, and sustained financial inputs. Facilities again showed no significant effect, likely due to the field-based nature of recovery operations.

Table 17 integrates all thematic areas and confirms that manpower ($B = 0.532$), facilities ($B = 0.133$), and budget ($B = 0.200$) significantly influence overall PDRRMO performance. Equipment, while important, did not reach statistical significance ($p = 0.062$), which may reflect inconsistent usage or deployment across provinces. These findings collectively highlight the indispensable role of human capital and resource availability in optimizing DRRM performance.

4. In Table 18, community members cited poor coordination among DRRM personnel (19.39) and inadequate distribution of IEC materials (18.37) as key obstacles during disaster prevention and mitigation. These issues suggest a need for greater inclusivity and responsiveness in community engagement and education.

In Table 19, the primary issue is the inadequate dissemination of public information (23.47), followed by a lack of DRMM-related training (14.29) in disaster preparedness.

Table 20 identifies logistical deficiencies as the main challenge during disaster response. The lack of ambulances and patient transport (29.59), poor inter-agency coordination (17.35), and

insufficient roadside assistance (16.33) reflect gaps in emergency mobility and field coordination. This underscores the need for enhanced logistical planning, inter-agency cooperation, and acquisition of critical transport equipment.

In Table 21, the most pressing post-disaster concerns include inadequate rehabilitation and recovery programs (22.45) and limited psychosocial support (16.33).

Table 22 identifies a lack of manpower (48.57) as the most prevalent internal challenge, followed by community hesitancy to evacuate (42.86) and weak resilience despite previous disaster experiences. Insufficient DRRM vehicles and communication gaps were also noted, pointing to systemic constraints in logistics, human resources, and stakeholder engagement.

Aggregates these concerns, showing that across all DRRM phases, the most recurrent challenges are inadequate distribution of IEC materials, lack of emergency equipment, and limited psychosocial support. In addition, the lack of manpower is the most prevalent internal challenge.

5. Table 23 highlights the need to resolve poor coordination, inadequate communication tools, and inadequate IEC distribution in disaster prevention and mitigation efforts. Proposed measures include the adoption of multi-channel communication systems, upgrade equipment, and planned IEC dissemination. These interventions, supported by coordination among the DILG, LGUs, NDRRMC, DRRMOs, and DBM.

In Table 24, disaster preparedness issues such as weak warning dissemination, insufficient community training, and poor clearing operations are addressed through enhanced public education, continuous drills, and improved coordination mechanisms. The proposed interventions center on inclusivity, community empowerment, and inter-agency synergy, involving agencies like the DPWH, PNP, BFP, and DepEd. These measures aim to build a culture of preparedness that is participatory, responsive, and comprehensive across sectors.

Table 25 addresses major logistical gaps in disaster response, notably the lack of ambulances, inadequate collaboration, and poor roadside assistance. Recommendations include ambulance procurement, inter-agency coordination, and creation of dedicated roadside assistance units. These strategies underscore the importance of operational readiness and fast mobility, especially during life-threatening emergencies. Enhancing physical resources and organizing simulation-based response activities are crucial steps toward a more efficient and synchronized emergency response system.

In Table 26, post-disaster recovery solutions target poor disaster rehabilitation and rehabilitation interventions, limited psychosocial support, and poor assistance in medical and outreach programs. Measures such comprehensive development, community engagement, and strengthening partnerships. These interferences emphasize that recovery must encompass beyond infrastructure repair to involve mental health support and economic renewal, ensuring an all-rounded and dignified approach to community rehabilitation. Maintainable recovery pivots on inclusivity, transparency, and tactical planning.

Finally, table 27 projected organizational transformations within the PDRMOs, particularly in counter internal tests or challenges such as manpower, shortages, community disentanglement, and tenacious vulnerabilities. Results include the institutionalization of DRRM positions, inclusive training and drills, and prolonged IEC campaigns. These projections or proposals distinguish the necessity of capitalizing in permanent human resources and fostering thrust by incessant community involvement, particularly among vulnerable groups. Institutional continuity, capability-building, and public involvement are crucial to building long-term resilience.

6. The results show that the key component of devolved governance is effective DRRM, which necessitates that LGUs, particularly the PDRMOs, have sufficiently resourced and qualified manpower.

7. The performance of PDRRMOs demonstrates a Very Satisfactory rating across all the DRRM pillars, which reflects a consistently high grand mean. Overall, while the PDRRMOs are performing commendably, a shift toward inclusive, sustainable, and community-centered strategies is imperative to ensure resilience across all phases of DRRM.

Recommendations

In light of these findings, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. Strengthen capacity building and professional development. Provide regular training or specialized training for DRRM personnel, with a focus on emergency logistics, planning, coordination, and modern technologies (e.g., GIS, hazard mapping, and automated early warning systems).
2. Institutionalize plan review and simulation. Conduct periodic reviews, updates, and simulation exercises of DRRM plans to ensure compliance with current risks and response protocols.
3. Enhance the coordination of DRRM and CCA in development and infrastructure planning at all levels of local governance. For instance, improve psychosocial support systems by training personnel and incorporating mental health services into emergency response plans; establish robust and accessible disaster financing and insurance programs for vulnerable communities; invest in infrastructure resiliency through retrofitting and building of disaster-resistant public buildings and housing; strengthen early recovery and livelihood restoration programs, particularly for disaster-affected families and small businesses;
4. Expand community-based capacity-building programs, such as public information campaigns, and regular disaster drills, including lectures, training, and evacuation drills.
5. Bolster public participation in DRRM. Develop local communities in DRRM planning and implementation to build trust and ownership. Address community hesitancy through education on the importance of evacuating and disaster risks.
6. Strengthen inter-agency collaboration, including partnerships with Provincial Hospital, LGUs, private organizations, and civil society groups for integrated DRRM services.
7. Utilize regular monitoring and evaluation of DRRM activities to ensure effectiveness, adaptability, and sustainability.
8. Enhance or strengthen human resource capacity. Recruit additional employees for the PDRRMOs to address the lack of manpower. Building a pool of skilled manpower will ensure operational readiness across all DRRM phases.
9. Enhance and maintain equipment. Regular assessment and modernization of rescue, communication, and logistical equipment should be prioritized to provide efficient disaster response and recovery.
10. Plan long-term financial strategies for readiness, resilience, and recovery.
11. Modernize equipment, invest in durable rescue tools, and establish integrated DRRM command and shelter stations.
12. Improve infrastructure and facility use. Disaster-related facilities still play a role in organizational coordination. Investments in multi-use DRRM hubs or mobile command centers could improve functionality.
13. Advocate for increased DRRM funding from local and national governments, especially to the most disaster-prone provinces. In addition, explore partnerships with NGOs and private entities to provide financial and technical assistance.

14. Upgrade search, rescue, and response services. Develop specialized response teams equipped with updated training and resources, and develop roadside assistance units and enhance the management of search and rescue operations.
15. Prioritize disaster rehabilitation and recovery. Integrate psychological first aid, medical operations, and livelihood programs in the recovery phase. Ensure that the operation and infrastructure restoration of disasters is completed promptly.

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